

Crystal Growth, Crystal Structure, Phase Transition and Optical Properties of 5FSA

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Abstract:

Organic crystal of 5-fluorosalicylaldehyde with Aniline were grown by solvent evaporation techniques at room temperature. The grown crystals were characterized through single crystal X-ray diffraction study and TG/DSC study. The crystal structure analyzed by single XRD and the crystal system is monoclinic system and the unit cell parameters are Space group= $p2_1lc$, $a=18.965(2)$, $b=4.7214$, $c=12.2399$, $\beta =107.881(7)$, $V(A^3)=1043.0(2)$, $Z=4$. TG/DSC studies confirm that phase transition. DSC was taken to study the structural phase transitions occurring in the crystals. The TG curve of the sample shows a prolonged decomposition from 73.2^oC and 210 °C, from which the decomposition pattern has been formulated. The endothermic peaks in the DTG curve indicate melting and decomposition of the compound at 296.2^oC and 388 °C respectively. An exothermic peak in low temperature DSC indicates a phase transition in the compound at 73.2 °C. The crystal shows three transitions above room temperature.

Keywords

Crystal structure, phase transition, TG/DSC, Thermal analysis and 5-FSA